

Studies on the Effect of Phosphate, EDTA and Added Micronutrient on the Availability of Zinc in Soil

ASIT KUMAR PAL and BISWANATH DAS

Department of Agril. Chemistry and Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswa Vidyalaya,
Kalyani, West Bengal

Manuscript received 22 August 1979, accepted 9 January 1980

The DTPA-extractable zinc status of two alluvial soils on incubation at moisture saturation under native and fertilized conditions have been studied. It was found that the application of a lower dose of phosphate caused an immediate increase in available Zn in both native and Zn treated soils but with higher dose of phosphate and on prolonged incubation a general decrease was observed. On adding organic matter as EDTA, phosphate treated soils showed an increase but one of the Zn-treated soils showed a decreasing trend which is the general case for all soils on prolonged incubation.

MICRONUTRIENT elements in plant nutrition are of great consequence in agricultural practices. Most of the arable soils are generally well supplied with micronutrients but their availability to plants being dependent on various factors and general plant requirement for these elements being low both deficiency and toxicity effects of them are often encountered. In recent years, the interest in micronutrients has increased because of the increasing consumption of fertilizers, intensive cropping and use of high yielding varieties.

As the ultimate source of micronutrients is the soil, it is necessary to know the available micronutrient status of the soil and the effect of various treatments on the change of availability of such micronutrients. Among the various methods, the DTPA-extraction developed by Lindsay and Norvell¹ has been found to be best correlated with the plant uptake.

Mandal and Das² carried out moisture incubation studies on the changes in DTPA-extractable Fe, Mn and Cu status of a few alluvial soils. The present investigation has been undertaken to study the effects of phosphatic and zinc fertilizers with or without an added chelating organic reagent like EDTA on the changes in DTPA-extractable zinc level in two soils of West Bengal on incubation for different periods at moisture saturated condition.

Experimental

Soils: Two soils used in the present investigation were obtained from a farm at Kalyani (K-soil) and from a village of Burdwan (B-soil) respectively. The fields from which the upper 23-cm layer of the soils were collected are under the programme of intensive cultivation. Both the soils are light to medium-textured and belong to recent Gangetic alluvium which have no sharp profile development. The soils were air-dried, ground and sieved through 80-mesh sieve and

analysed for various physico-chemical properties which are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SOILS

Mechanical composition	Kalyani soil	Burdwan soil
Sand %	57.50	47.35
Silt %	5.00	6.00
Clay %	37.50	44.00
pH	7.80	6.70
Total Nitrogen %	0.12	0.10
Organic carbon %	0.76	0.75
CEC, me/100 g	9.96	14.70
Saturation percentage	45.20	39.06
Available phosphorus (ppm)	2.75	1.50
Available manganese (ppm)	15.10	35.10
Available zinc (ppm)	1.60	1.20

Treatments and procedure: Each soil was mixed with a basal dose of nitrogen as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ and potassium as KCl (N=75 ppm, K_2O = 50 ppm) and divided into two main parts. One part was kept as control while the other part was treated with one or more of the following substances: 50 ppm P_2O_5 as single superphosphate (P_1), 100 ppm P_2O_5 (P_2), 2 gm EDTA per kg of soil (OM_1) and 20 ppm Zn as $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Zn_1).

After thorough mixing, 1 kg of each soil sample were taken in plastic pots. Each of these treated and control samples had three replications. These were

moisture saturated by adding de-ionized water and subjected to incubation for different periods of time such as 1 day, 7 days and 30 days. No holes were left at the bottom of the pots to prevent leaching of the nutrients and the pots were covered with polythene sheets to prevent any loss of moisture.

Weighed portions (about 10 gm) of soil were sampled out with a spoon-headed spatula after each incubation period for extraction of zinc with DTPA extractant.

Extraction: The soil (10.0 gm) was shaken with 20 ml of the DTPA-extractant solution for 2 hours and filtered. To the filtrate 3 ml of conc. nitric acid and 5 ml of conc. sulphuric acid were added and the resulting solution was digested on a hot plate. Another 2 ml of conc. HNO₃ were added until all the organic matter and the metal-DTPA chelates completely decomposed. The resulting material was taken with redistilled water and the volume was made upto mark in 50-ml volumetric flask. Appropriate aliquots were taken from this solution for the estimation of zinc by standard colorimetric methods.

Estimation of zinc. DTPA-extractable zinc was determined by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer using acetylene-air flame and a zinc hollow cathode.

Total zinc was estimated colorimetrically by dithi-zone method following the procedure as described by Black³.

A Klett-Summerson double beam colorimeter was used for all color absorbance measurements.

All the chemicals and reagents used were of A. R. quality.

Results and Discussion

The effect of addition of two different doses of phosphate on the quantity of DTPA-extractable zinc in native and the micronutrient treated soils are shown in Table-2. The changes in the amount of available zinc are also shown graphically in Figs. 1 and 2.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARIOUS TREATMENTS ON THE AVAILABILITY OF ZINC (PPM) IN SOIL

Treatments	K-soil			B-soil		
	Days of incubation			Days of incubation		
	1	7	30	1	7	30
Zn ₀ P ₀ OM ₀	2.80	2.30	1.70	2.50	2.10	2.30
Zn ₀ P ₁ OM ₀	3.50	2.40	1.80	2.70	2.20	2.70
Zn ₀ P ₂ OM ₀	2.50	2.30	1.90	3.00	2.40	2.00
Zn ₁ P ₀ OM ₁	5.30	2.80	2.20	3.40	2.60	4.10
Zn ₀ P ₁ OM ₁	3.90	2.60	1.70	3.70	2.20	2.40
Zn ₀ P ₂ OM ₁	6.00	3.10	2.90	4.30	2.60	2.50
Zn ₁ P ₀ OM ₀	8.80	8.50	4.60	4.40	4.05	1.50
Zn ₁ P ₁ OM ₀	13.50	5.20	1.80	4.50	4.95	2.10
Zn ₁ P ₂ OM ₀	11.20	4.00	3.40	6.40	5.10	2.50
Zn ₁ P ₀ OM ₁	7.50	6.50	3.60	8.50	3.50	1.20
Zn ₁ P ₁ OM ₁	9.00	3.10	1.90	7.50	9.90	3.30
Zn ₁ P ₂ OM ₁	6.00	4.00	3.30	6.00	10.30	2.70

It was found that there was an immediate increase in DTPA-extractable zinc in both native and Zn-treated

Fig 1. Effect of different levels of P on DTPA-extractable Zn in native soils

□ P₀ ○ P₁ △ P₂

Fig. 2. Effect of different levels of P on DTPA-extractable Zn in Zn treated soils

□ P₀ ○ P₁ △ P₂

soils, especially when a lower dose (50 ppm P₂O₅) of phosphate was applied. The effect was more conspicuous in Kalyani soil (K-soil). In Burdwan soil (B-soil) however, even higher doses of applied phosphate caused an increase in available zinc. This may be due to lowering of pH associated with the addition of phosphate in the form of superphosphate. Laker⁴ also reported that the application of high phosphate level increased the content of extractable zinc.

On incubation for 7 days, extractable zinc content was decreased in both the soils with higher doses of phosphate. This is obviously due to chemical precipitation as a result of increased pH and phosphate ion activity coupled with fixation in smectite dominated clay lattice.

On prolonging the period of incubation upto 30 days a further decrease was observed in all cases except the B-soil treated with lower dose of superphosphate. In comparison with the control series soil samples treated with higher dose of phosphate showed a smaller decrease in DTPA-extractable zinc. With Zn-treated soils, sharper decrease was observed in case of lower dose of applied phosphate.

It appears that on prolonging incubation while the applied phosphate does not alter much the available zinc status of the alluvial soils, most of the added fertilizer zinc is transformed into unavailable pool, especially when a lower dose of superphosphate is applied to the soil.

The effect of addition of organic matter as EDTA on zinc availability in soil is shown in Table 2 and changes in available zinc in the soils on incubation for different periods are shown graphically in Figs. 3 and 4.

It can be seen that on adding EDTA the DTPA-extractable Zn content immediately increases in both the phosphate treated soils. The effect was more pronounced in K-soil. In case of Zn-treated soil, however, while the B-soil showed a general increase, the K-soil exhibited a decreasing trend. The increase is due to mobilization of the less labile micronutrient pool through the chelating effect of EDTA. A somewhat similar observation was made by Elgawhary *et al*⁵. The decrease in extractable Zn is due to fixation of added zinc in the clay mineral lattice or immobilization of the element as insoluble phosphates or basic

Fig. 3. Effect of OM and P on DTPA-extractable Zn in native soils

Fig. 4. Effect of OM and P on DTPA-extractable Zn in Zn treated soils

phosphates at the relatively higher pH of the soil in question.

On incubation for 7 days, a general decrease in DTPA-extractable Zn was noticed in all cases, particularly when no Zn-fertilizer was added. In case of Zn-treated and phosphate fertilized B-soil, however, an increase in extractable Zn content was observed. The decrease may be due to conversion of Zn-EDTA complex to more stable Fe^{III}-EDTA complex with the resulting immobilization of soluble zinc as shown below :

Since EDTA is somewhat resistant to decomposition at a relatively higher pH the above general reaction proceeds towards the right hand side. At a lower pH,

however, more zinc is mobilized from the non-labile pool which causes an increase in available zinc.

On prolonging incubation, extractable zinc status was decreased in all soil samples. This is obviously due to chemical or microbial decomposition of EDTA and the reaction of the type shown above resulting in the fixation of labile zinc. Both the native and zinc treated soils were found to behave in a similar manner even under the phosphate fertilized conditions.

References

1. W. L. LINDSAY and W. A. NORVELL, *Agron. Abs.*, 1969, p. 84.
2. A. K. MANDAL and B. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 93.
3. C. A. BLACK, *Methods of Soil Analysis, Part-2*, Amer. Soc. Agro. Inc., Madison, Wisconsin, USA, 1965.
4. M. C. LAKER, *S. Afr. J. Agric. Sci.*, 1967, 10, 323-330.
5. S. M. ELGAWHARY, W. L. LINDSAY and W. D. KEMPER, *S. S. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1970, 34, 66-70.